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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

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ERA POLICY BRIEF

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TOPIC: SUPPORT FOR THE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION DIMENSION OF EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES (PART II)

PROJECT: ENLIGHT Research and Innovation agenda with and for SociEty (ENLIGHT RISE)

<https://enlight-eu.org/>

SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

In this policy brief, the European Universities pilot alliances report on the progress made through cooperation in selected R&I areas and provide a first set of recommendations to the European Commission for further policy development.

Policy background:

In order to strengthen strategic partnerships across the EU amongst higher education institutions, the European Commission targets the emergence of “European Universities” by 2024 by funding alliances from across Europe. The ambitious mandate aims to trigger systemic, structural and sustainable institutionalized cooperation between higher education institutions. As a complement to the Erasmus+ action geared towards supporting higher education cooperation models, Horizon 2020 support is dedicated to contributing to the research and innovation dimension of the alliances between European universities, in line with their shared, integrated, long-term joint strategy and in synergy with their education dimension.

This initiative is one of the flagships of the European strategy for universities that aims at supporting and enabling universities to adapt to changing conditions, to thrive and to take a leading role in the recovery of Europe, and in making our society greener, more inclusive and more digital. The adoption of this strategy was accompanied by a Commission proposal for a Council recommendation on building bridges for effective European higher education cooperation.

In parallel, the European Research Area Policy Agenda sets out 20 voluntary actions for the period 2022-2024, including several of which are relevant for universities. The feedback from the alliances will help co-shape the design and implementation of the ERA Policy Agenda 2022 – 2024, such as ERA actions 1 (sharing of data), 3 (reform of research management), 4 (strengthening careers), 5 (gender equality), 7 (knowledge valorisation), 8 (research infrastructures), 13 (empowering universities), 14 (engaging citizens), 15 (role in R&I ecosystem), 17 (research management capacity).

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS

Challenges encountered by the Alliance.

One alliance, two projects

Through the ENLIGHT RISE project and its R&I dimension, the ENLIGHT European University alliance seeks to deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda, in synergy with the educational component supported by Erasmus+, and in partnership with its surrounding ecosystems (businesses, civil society, governments). One of the challenges we faced as an Alliance was the different timelines and different funding of the 2 projects. Although both projects have a different goal, overlapping happens on several topics (PhD students, public engagement, relationships with the surrounding ecosystems, transdisciplinary core groups etc.). In addition, due to the pandemic, the research management community could not meet at the start of the project and the first meetings in real life took place only at M9 and 10.

Resources and long-term approach

Creating alliances of European universities and setting a joint research agenda are ambitious goals. This high level of ambition and challenges require a long-term view – shared by all the universities, and adequate and sustainable funding. The 3-year timeline of the SwafS funding is extremely short, and the absence of information regarding the future of the funding is problematic to envision a long-term approach.

Due to the limited funding, there is a lack of sufficient resources and dedicated support staff in each of the partner universities. Personnel was foreseen and budgeted on the project, however, we notice that being an institutional project, its implementation impacts a lot of departments/units/staff of our universities. Some tasks require to involve additional staff who already have a heavy workload. In addition, the large number of deliverables shifts the focus from communication and community building to producing numerous and large documents. Lack of funding also means that we cannot develop as good (digital and other) solutions for the alliance (and in particular, its researchers) as we would like to.

Setting up sustainable long term scientific collaborations within the ENLIGHT alliance takes a lot of time. Within each partner university, effort needs to be made to convey the idea that this initiative is not only a project but is an instrument to jointly develop and promote transformations at the level of each partner university. It is important to demonstrate the added-value of the alliance, which could prove especially challenging with researchers, as successful researchers have already established collaborations through their own international networks. We noticed that it takes time to acculturate the research community to ENLIGHT. It will take several years to build trust between research communities within the alliance, and trust is a basic requirement to set up and maintain long-term scientific cooperation.

The limited European funding, the lack of extra financial support of some Member States, and the budgetary constraints faced by universities lead to a situation where there is not enough budget and time to fully initiate an ambitious research vision for the alliance.

Differences between the 9 partners in terms of internal organisation, research culture, and levels of involvement/engagement in specific topics

We noticed vast disparities in definition of concepts, approaches to handle topics, internal governance and administrative hierarchy. There were also technical day-to-day challenges such as communication channels or software to use. These divergences slow down the progress as they are often a source of misunderstandings and confusions hampering the cooperation.

One example to illustrate this challenge is our work on Impact. Impact is by its own nature context-dependent, resulting in multiple understandings, approaches and policies to promote impactful R&I. The approach taken by partner universities to Research Impact and how or even if it is incorporated into an overall Institutional Policy Framework is quite diverse. Impact may also look and operate slightly differently across disciplines, and for fundamental versus applied research. Besides, the arena of impact is a minefield of terminology, with different countries, organisations, and funders adopting general or very specific vocabulary (e.g. knowledge mobilization, knowledge exchange, research uptake, valorisation, etc.).

There is also a fragmentation of knowledge in partner universities and a need to build bridges between different units (e.g. Open Science-OS, rewards and recognition). It is also crucial to stay up to date and to raise awareness about ENLIGHT topics of interest, policies and practices at the international, European, national and institutional levels and to inform and align the approach of ENLIGHT (e.g. OS, Impact, Digital research infrastructures (DRI) etc.).

Some staff in our universities face difficulties to participate due to their lack of comfort in English. Multilingualism is important but in such a project, the English language is the only vector.

Good practices and tangible progress that individual partners as well as the Alliance as a whole have made in terms of introducing changes in their entities as a result of this project.

18 months is a short period of time to introduce institutional changes. It is a long-term effort that requires time and continuous dedication. However, good progress has been made and is promising for the future.

The first year of the project was mainly dedicated to better know the research culture, priorities, profiles of each partner. Only a good understanding of the existing status can lay the foundations for a strong cooperation that might lead to institutional changes.

Initial mapping exercises provided a good overview of the diverse activities and strategies of the ENLIGHT partners and where they see opportunities for actions and alignment. It was very important to understand the position of each partner university, to create a sound working basis and a trustful environment, whilst respecting their specifics, policies and approaches. It leads to knowledge sharing and mutual learning established in ENLIGHT that has already been beneficial to the partners.

- Potential R&I synergies were identified through a mapping of the scientific and technological profiles of each university - using public available databases.
- The [ENLIGHT R&I observatory](#) is being created as a one stop shop containing an overview of the scientific expertise at each alliance university, the R&I synergies and the project outputs.
- The [ENLIGHT repository of good practices on research impact](#) brings together in a single place good practices of impact assessment and measurement, both in the context of ENLIGHT universities and worldwide.
- Mapping exercises were also conducted on public engagement, Open Science (the OS Matrix), DRI, impact (Impact landscaping exercise, Impact Literacy Survey), Research and Support Offices (RSO) practices, Innovation district.
- Workshops on best practices or on specific topics, as well as trainings and networking events contribute to mutual learning on our topics of interest: RSO, DRI, DI/AI, early career researchers, innovation, research assessment, public engagement, OS, impact.
- Several toolkits are published or expected during the second year: the ENLIGHT self-assessment tool on universities research impact, support kit for researchers, starter kit on OS.

Emphasis has been made on creating a community within the project and the alliance and increase mobility.

- Regular meetings bringing together colleagues on our topics of interest (RSO, R&I synergies, DRI, research assessment and early career researchers, Innovation, public engagement, OS, Impact) help to exchange knowledge and best practices, report on progress and coordinate next steps. It also creates opportunities for synergies among partners.
- Transdisciplinary focus groups of researchers and RSO staff are being installed and aim to exchange research ideas, to get more familiar with each other scientific ecosystems & priorities and foster competitive consortia in the future.
- A network of OS Ambassadors and Impact Ambassadors provide additional insights into current needs and challenges as well as incentives and barriers for researchers to engage in these two fields. They are also linked to the creation of awards on OS and Impact. These initiatives are also useful to give some spotlight on the alliance within each partner university.
- On a competitive basis seed money is provided to support mobility between research groups. Some universities also decided to set up budgets (often funded by national – regional ministries) to foster collaboration and promote mobility.
- ENLIGHT Events: AIMDay and the ENLIGHT Impact Conference, workshops (e.g. on DRIs, research assessment).
- To align the two projects involved in the ENLIGHT alliance, joint governance and staff meetings (directors' meeting, joint bi-annual general meetings) as well as events (European Dialogue/AIMday, ENLIGHT lecture series) are organised together with the E+ community. There is also a growing involvement of the vice presidents and vice rectors of Research.

- Within each university, regular meetings with all staff involved in the project aim to inform regularly about the alliance and foster engagement and involvement in this initiative.

Special attention has been given to communicate about the content and tools developed by the project within our universities but also for other stakeholders: the ENLIGHT website is constantly updated and results (deliverables and other relevant documents) are published in open access on the [ENLIGHT RISE Zenodo community](#). Language courses were offered within the alliance for staff, as well as internal training in some universities.

Another good practice has been the creation of the FOREU2 Swafs subgroup and the FOREU2 impact thematic subgroup, which has given the participating alliances the opportunity to share common challenges and propose innovative solutions to those challenges.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Policy topic 1: facilitating transnational cooperation

- Knowing that the Commission proposed a Council recommendation to facilitate transnational collaboration between universities, which action should be prioritised to address the challenges you encountered as an Alliance in sharing capacities, infrastructures, resources or staff in R&I?

Long-term funding is needed to ensure the success of alliances in their various dimension (education, research, innovation, transfer to society), as highlighted in the Joint statement of the 41 European Universities Alliances released in March 2022. While including the R&I dimension in the new E+ proposal was decided by our alliance, no dedicated funding for alliances' R&I dimension is detrimental to ensure true and sustainable transformation on the R&I aspects.

Dedicated funding could be made available only for the alliances to support bottom-up collaborations by funding joint research projects preferably allowing to address curiosity-driven research topics of mutual interest to the project partners.

Participation in alliances could also be given extra points in the Horizon Europe (HE) evaluation system. Activities involving public engagement also should be highlighted in the evaluation process. A centralized joint management of R&I calls for research projects/research support within the alliance (instead of separate seed funding in some universities) could be imagined through HE calls dedicated to university alliances (partnership type) whereby the EC co-funds the set-up of a joint call for proposal by university alliances (cascade funding), call for proposals open to researchers from the given alliance with an independent evaluation system - a bit like ERANET/partnerships calls. It could foster strong communities of researchers and academics within alliances.

A key to the success of transnational cooperation in R&I relies on experienced researchers, as well as on PhD students and early career researchers (ECR). There should be lower barriers of the recognition of skills and trainings in degree structures and life-long learning (offered by various staff types in universities). Incentives are needed to extend the ECRs networks (beyond the MSCA scheme).

Further improvement can be done on the rights retention and exceptions for research and harmonisation of legal frameworks that are relevant for research, teaching and learning (with open licensing of publications, data, code, etc.).

We would also highlight the importance of Recommendation 10 *“Encourage higher education institutions to involve learners, academics and researchers more in the governance of higher education institutional transnational cooperation structures”*

2. Policy topic 2: strengthening careers

- Is there a need to develop a model tenure-track system at European level to contribute to solving precariousness of early career researchers? If you believe so, how do you think it should be structured?

If carefully designed and monitored, a tenure track system could be an instrument to tackle the precariousness and the lack of stability in the careers of early career researchers, and to provide clearer career perspectives to ECRs in a transnational context. It will, however, be a challenge to design a model that is conceived with due respect for the autonomy of the universities to recruit academic staff, and that overcomes the existing differences in academic (and sometimes also in legal) systems.

A suitable model for a tenure-track system would provide more clarity to both existing and prospective academic staff of the value and importance we place on academic careers. It could encourage universities and other research institutions in Europe to rethink their current approaches.

It would be extremely useful to have consistency across the EU in how universities use and implement the roles of Assistant, Associate and full Professor. The main piece of work would be the agreement of a set of competencies for such roles to demonstrate to applicants what knowledge, skills and behaviours our universities/EU require - the competencies should not be too restrictive and should incorporate data gleaned from the working groups linked to research assessment. This in turn would facilitate more mobility across the sector - indeed, mobility could be included as a part of the journey to tenure allowing for various levels of mobility to suit people at varying career/personal stages. Such a system should not only cover research positions but also positions that are essential for the management of research workflows, management and curation of research outputs, teaching and learning (e.g. data stewardship, research software engineering, challenged-based teaching, open education).

- In light of the policy process on the reform of assessment of research and institutions, what are your recommendations on how to address academic/researcher career assessment?

The partner universities acknowledge the importance to reform the research assessment system, and broadly support the reform process that is called for by the ‘coalition of the willing’. A dedicated Research Assessment Working Group in ENLIGHT RISE follows up on the European initiative (Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment - CoARA), and compares assessment systems across the alliance. Several partner universities have taken steps to reform their assessment practices and several members have joined the CoARA¹. The research assessment systems in the partner universities vary considerably. Although moving towards the same direction, the different universities are also at different stages in the process of reforming their assessment systems. Reforming research assessment requires a cultural change inside each of the organisations concerned, as well as the support of the research communities and the agreement of national regulating authorities. That is why ENLIGHT RISE welcomes the common direction as set out by the CoARA, but also adheres to the autonomy of the universities to design and follow their own reform process.

Academic/researcher career assessments should recognize and reward achievements broadly, i.e. in terms of the diversity of research outputs (publications, data, code, etc.) and the activities (research design and implementation, data collection/processing, data stewardship, mentoring, teaching, software development, innovation and applications, peer review, reproduction and replication, etc.). It should also recognise researchers’ efforts in planning for and achieving impact, including the efforts to engage with societal stakeholders and ensure gender equality, equal opportunities and inclusiveness. Regarding the process, it is vital to ensure engagement and to capture a diverse range of academic career experiences across the sector that academic staff at all levels are included in the design for implementation of research assessment.

¹ University of Bordeaux, Comenius University Bratislava, University of Galway, Ghent University, University of Groningen

3. Policy topic 3: digital transition

- What are the specific needs of the alliances to accelerate their digital transition in the R&I dimension, and how can this be addressed at the EU level?
- In particular, do you see a need for *additional* dedicated e-infrastructures for data storage and management that are distributed and interoperable? Please take into account progress regarding the development of the federated e-infrastructure for research outputs (EOSC, see [ERA Policy Agenda](#)), and the implementation of a digital platform for cooperation in higher education (see the [European strategy for universities](#)).

Resources are needed to create better joint digital systems. ENLIGHT RISE is working on a digital matching tool for funding/researcher and researcher/researcher matching. However, the resources for its development are extremely limited (both financial and staff). Researchers of our alliance also expressed an interest in a joint researcher database that would help them easily find potential collaborators from within the alliance.

However, it should be avoided that each of the +40 alliances develop their own dedicated e-infrastructures as this will cost a lot of money and hampers the exchange of knowledge among the alliances. It would be useful that the EU could take steps in this to define the framework for such e-infrastructures in order to reduce the variability of systems that will be developed.

A point of attention on this topic is sensitive data and GDPR. To facilitate cooperation between the higher education institutions, they need to agree on a common legally sustainable interpretation of GDPR's definition of personal data, how they define sensitive personal data, pseudonymized data and anonymized data and what are the requirements for handling data, specifically sensitive personal data. Agreeing on this in advance would form an essential basis for a collaboration around data (both in education and research). Then, a correct level of security for handling and exchanging sensitive data (encryption and two-factor authentication) is needed. Utilization of federated data analyses with DataShield is an option if the universities, for some reason, find that it is not appropriate to send the data sets to each other. Within EOSC, the definition, needs, implementation of a "federated e-infrastructure" is not yet fully explored.

4. Policy topic 4: access to excellence

- What is your advice on how to accelerate access to excellence in science and in value creation for all participants for higher education institutions across the entire ERA, through the European Universities Initiative?

Alliances need to continue and further strengthen their approaches that aim at transparency and quality of research processes and outcomes (in particular: responsible open science), while paying attention to aspects of resource allocation, recognition and reward of all efforts (networking, sharing and building up expertise, skills and competences, sharing of federated e-infrastructures, etc.).

Calls that encourage collaboration across alliances could be beneficial for accelerating excellence and career development (e.g. piloting of collaborations, mentoring and training, setting up an integrated research information system bringing together internal information dealing with research output, ongoing research projects, new research ideas, HR-related information on research-performing staff, research infrastructure, etc.).

Excellence should be pursued not only by impact driven research but also the fundamental / curiosity driven research.

The definition of scientific excellence must not be narrowly defined by sole quantitative criteria alone but must also include qualitative, cultural and social dimensions so that the competition for scientific excellence is the same for regardless of their sex, gender, sexual orientation, nationality and ethnicity, the fact of having disability, their religion, social background or culture.

ENLIGHT RISE would like to stress the initiatives such as the regional academies bringing in external partners, and using challenges from the regions to develop research initiatives with input from existing and emerging research groups from across the network.

As stated by the European Commission, “Research performing entities, local ecosystems and regions who are proven strong and excellent hubs in knowledge creation and innovation usually rely on a strong community of R&I managers.”² Research support is essential to the development and outreach of scientific excellence, yet science management positions often remain invisible and/or linked with precarious career pathways. The EU has a central role to play to encourage member states and universities to invest in the research support staff, its skills development and offer better career perspective and recognition.

5. Policy topic 5: increasing global competitiveness

- Europe’s relative weight at a global level when it comes to research-intensive universities is shrinking. In light of this, a European Excellence Initiative will be established to improve global competitiveness of Europe’s universities, in synergy with the European Universities Initiative of Erasmus+. In your view, what would be key elements of such an Initiative? Secondly, could you envisage that such an initiative specifically targets EU objectives such as the Green Deal or European Missions?

ENLIGHT RISE welcomes the European Excellence initiative, nonetheless the programme as outlined in the WIDERA work programme might be too narrowly defined in terms of the composition of consortia (allow/encourage global collaborations) and ambitions (e.g. allow targeted collaborations on skills development and training, based on opening up infrastructures and expertise).

Regarding the EU objectives, they are of course important and over time the researchers in the alliance will get to know each other better and will benefit from the extra opportunities offered by the EU in support of the EU objectives such as the Green Deal or European Missions. However, we should be cautious in targeting investments on selected fields of research. European research should be strong on a broad variety of topics.

6. Other recommendations

Advocacy is needed for an established and long-term financial support to alliances from Member States. The alliance projects are not classical ones in that sense that they are not intended to come into effect for a certain period of time: on the contrary, they are supposed to transform permanently the partner institutions in their way of collectively conducting training, education and doing research. To make these transformative projects credible and supported by all communities, they have to demonstrate their strong added value, and this is why significant funding is necessary, at least at the beginning, for a few years, in order to promote and support staff, student and academic mobility as well as various original joint projects. Alliances have to implement new ways, new visions to conduct collaborations. On the basis of the joint results/successes achieved, it is hoped that national funding agencies in all European countries will become increasingly involved to support alliances in a sustainable way. This national support will be facilitated if a sustainable and long-term funding mechanism for alliances is established at the EU level.

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² [European Research Area Policy Agenda \(2022 – 2024\)](#)